

Human Identity and Its Negotiation with Reference to Subaltern: A Study of Tabish Khair's *The Bus Stopped*

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Abstract

Identity is a set of meanings or symbols which describe what a person is individually and in the roles prescribed by a group or society and how he is different from others. It may be temporary or long-lasting and thus cannot be decided or fixed always. Tabish Khair foregrounds various types and nuances of identity and its related conflicting issues in his novels. The present paper analyzes his fictional work, namely, *The Bus Stopped* which portrays man's struggle to cope with the harsh realities and his association with his native land.

Keywords: *Hybrid, Identity, Negotiation, Subaltern, Tolerance*

Identity is a set of meanings or symbols which describe what a person is individually and in the roles prescribed by a group or society and how he is different from others. The word 'identity' derives its meaning traditionally with Eric Erikson's theory in the 1950s after which it was used with varied connotations and definitions in many social science disciplines by the 1970s and is now associated with different cultural, racial, political, sexual, gender and diasporic meanings in post-modern era. It lends vast but complex and sometimes contradictory leanings to the idea of identity. Hogg and Abrams define identity as "people's concepts of who they are, of what sort of people they are, and how they relate to others" (2). In contrary to the traditional psychologists carrying the concept of a stable, secure and determined identity, the postmodern theorists, critics and philosophers put forward an idea of multiple and often-conflicting identity constantly changing and relating to different interpretations as per the contextual requirements.

The question of identity arises very early in the life from the childhood stage when a child rooted firmly in his socio-cultural realities begins to express its personal choices and perceptions, comprehend its image as a social being, consider others' feedback. Identity is the essential sense of the 'self' of a person as an individual in interaction with others and as a member of some group. Self is not the identity itself but a major factor in making identity in the sense that it relates itself to the external socio-cultural background, status, traits, roles and bindings. A sense of belongingness or hatred also develops from this very truth. In reference to postmodernists, Merry comments that identity addresses only "indeterminate, mutable narratives of persons located within the social or cultural roles they are called upon to play" (1) but Wendt observes that identities are "relatively stable, role-specific understandings and expectations about self" (397). In fact, Moreover, it travels through various phases of growth as experiences bring changes in the vision of an individual about himself and others and also in the perception of others about that person.

Identities may be of many types including social identity, cultural identity, national identity, religious identity, personal identity, class identity, racial identity, gender identity, sexual identity, place identity, political identity and economic identity – all subject to a person's role, association, commitment and affiliation. It is not an exaggeration to say that hybrid identity is essential to create a personality which can assimilate, adopt and adapt with different environments. A prominent psychologist and chief theorist of identity thesis, Erikson defines identity both as personal and social construction due to a strong interplay existing between the psychic self and the social self. His concept of ego-identity accentuates the importance of personal growth and characteristics firstly and cultural and social roles secondly in making personal identity. The conflict between inner and outer worlds of a person gets started from his very adolescent stage and the potential of this conflict is based upon how an individual deals with it which significantly gives birth to either an integrated identity or a diffusive identity or identity crisis. A man is always divided between his social and personal identities though both are incorporated into each-other. The identity of subalterns has always been in question as the dominant groups had wiped out the narratives of the

exploited natives from the accepted histories because the subalterns have been too silent to foreground their miseries.

Tabish Khair, a diasporic and versatile Indian English writer, works with different genres including fiction, non-fiction, poetry, travelogue, drama, gothic writing, and transliteration of the established works with equal dexterity and thoughtfulness. He foregrounds various types and nuances of identity and its related conflicting issues in his novels. The present paper analyzes his fictional work, namely, *The Bus Stopped* which being immersed in the composite nature of Indian culture presents its asymmetrical living patterns along with universal themes and issues haunting human thoughts and feelings everywhere. In a familiar Indian atmosphere full of varied lively scenes, sounds and smells, Khair tries to portray man's struggle to cope with the harsh realities and his association with his native land. His focus is continuously on the depressed, unnoticed and othered beings and on the repugnant conditions making their survival suffocated. He expresses his belief in the negotiation of minority groups in respect of their identity-making and rehabilitation in the mainstream of the society. The orientation of the present paper is to highlight Khair's sensibility and sensitivity with which he narrates the common man's alienated existence in the process of identification and adaptation with social, cultural and economic surroundings.

The Bus presents a montage of various mini-narratives of common Indian life and binds them together through a journey from Gaya to Phansa in Bihar. The journey photographically portrays a lot of familiar aspects of Indian people through the tripartite structure of "Homes"; "Journeys" and "Homes, Again". The narrative structure is equally complex as different first person narrators are engaged by the writer to tell their personal experiences and highlight the common theme of identity. The journey becomes a meeting place of varied cultures, languages and living patterns which form new groupings and associations with an undertone of hybrid and multicultural existence and changing identity of man. In "Review Article", King appreciates the novel as, "Khair's social focus is shown by the idea and structure of *The Bus Stopped*, an update of the multivoiced, multicharacter community novel ... a vehicle for national and racial cultural assertion" (136). The significant reality of the human life as a voyage

responsible for the emergence of new identities is suggested through the large space given to the section “Journeys”. *The Bus* introduces a plethora of human characters sharing common Indian space but differing in their group affiliations in caste, class, sect and religion. All of these struggling continuously to prove their personal worth and identity in the given social and cultural conditions represent distinctiveness of their existence under the influence of external environment. They also try to create a balance among the paradoxes of Indian realities – hesitations and acceptances of daily boring life; old colonial and new professional relations; traditional customs and new developments in the post-colonial independent India.

The past royalty and grandeur of the kingly India and its decline with the passage of time are depicted through the character of Muslim narrator and his relations with the higher aristocratic class. Various mental depressions and stresses of the middle class people are highlighted through the characters of a refined woman Mrs. Mirchandani; her benign son Vijay Mirchandani; the smug but victimized Mrs Prasad; the influential but corrupt politician ministerji; and the family members of a junior-level government official, Mr. Sharma. The skilled working class with their professional exertion and strife is represented through the characters of the driver Mangal Singh; the conductor Shankar; the *khansama* Wazir Mian; and the taxi driver Hari. At the same time, the dilemmas of the underprivileged classes along with their heroic endeavours to sustain their life are delineated through the characters of the voluptuous maid Zeenat; the cleaning boy Rameshwar; the family servant turned criminal Chottu and the tribal woman. The unusual character of the astute eunuch Farhana Begum shows the harsh eccentricity of human life which is not easy to negotiate in the tradition-ridden society. The conflicting and complex identity of a diaspora is given voice in the character of the Danish, Rasmus who with his original roots in India and his abode in Denmark is divided between the two countries for his links and aspirations. The stories of all of these characters along with some other voices in the background of the novel are amalgamated to create a common platform where these people collaborating differently in various groups and combinations struggle to maintain their identity through negotiations and adaptations with the existing realities.

Khair talks about the multicultural and multilingual identity which is a better medium to connect people despite their internal and personal socio-religious and ethno-cultural differences and suggests that all creatures should understand each-other like in a single community. He gives shape to the plural identity by pointing out the mixing of cultures and languages which foregrounds hybrid type of personalities. Mythical anecdotes and religious associations of Indians keep them connected which contribute to the common identity with no biases at all in *The Bus*. Khair's elaboration of different myths, foods delicacies and joyful moments enjoyed commonly by all people irrespective of their religion, caste or status indicates their common identity as an Indian. Through their feeling of secularism, tolerance and brotherhood people try to negotiate their identity. Khair is very conspicuous in detailing the common experiences of racial, religious, social, gender- based, economic and political prejudices in *The Bus*. Various class struggles, ideological differences and cultural conflicts are discernible with Indian sensibility and global perspective to find out the possibilities of assertion of identity of minorities and migrants with the help of multilayered narratives, structure and multiplicity of characters and languages.

Man's identity fabricated with an interplay of being and becoming; subject and object; self and other is perceived to be a performative and flexible idea which undergoes shocking metamorphosis and depends upon the fortune reversal. The fate of Mrs Prasad, Farhana, Mangal Singh and Wazir Mian shows that appearances are deceptive but appearances have to be maintained. The culprit responsible for man's tragic displacement, ostracization and predicament is nobody other than the inner instincts of man. The weird and wearied existence of subalterns, their haunted dreams and desires, their stereotypical and subversive images find a platform in the novel to expose a ghastly reality of human life. However the message is confirmed that there is nothing permanent or stable – home, nation, ideology or identity because life is a journey -sometimes planned, sometimes sudden activity and so transitory also. King validates it, "Khair shows how unstable identity or claims to knowledge that do not take into account the basis of its production are. Money and power create hierarchies and discourses concerning class, race, reason, and other characteristics" (*Rewriting* 173).

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Accepting the universal reality of 'gypsy identity', everyone has to think over the inclusion of vulnerable and subaltern in the hierarchical social set-up for their comfortable co- existence in view of transculturation and transnational living. *The Bus* underlines that a society with a motive of equality in sharing and caring, humanity in behaviour, progression upwardly and movement ahead only can be accepted in the changing scenario.

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